

When Robotics Meets Distributed Learning: the Federated Learning Robotic Network Framework

Roberto Marino, Lorenzo Carnevale, Massimo Villari

University of Messina, Messina, Italy

{roberto.marino, lcarnevale, mvillari}@unime.it

Abstract—Federated Learning (FL) is a cutting-edge technology for distributed solving of large-scale problems using local data exclusively. The potential of Federated Learning is nowadays clear in different context from automatic analysis of healthcare data to object recognition in video sources coming from public video streams, from distributed search for data breach and finance frauds to collaborative learning of hand typing on mobile phone. Multi-robot systems can also largely benefit from FL concerning resolution of problems like trajectory prediction, non colliding trajectory generation, distributed localization and mapping or distributed reinforcement learning. In this paper we propose a multi-robot framework that includes distributed learning capabilities by using Decentralized Stochastic Gradient Descent on graphs. First of all we motivate the position of the paper discussing the privacy preserving problem for multi robot systems and the need of decentralized learning. Then we build our methodology starting from a set of prior definitions. Finally we discuss in details the possible applications in robotics field.

Index Terms—Multi Robot Systems, Federated Learning, Machine Learning, Distributed Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous Mobile Robots are day-by-day growing their impact in human life. From fleets of self-driving cars, passing from packs of robotic dogs in hazardous environment, coming to fleets of unmanned aerial vehicles in disaster scenarios, the needs of autonomous systems able to coordinates on common tasks are actually becoming a technology breakthrough. At the same time, the sensor's precision, rate and heterogeneity are dramatically increasing the amount and complexity of data that have to be processed, with subsequent high demand of computational power, storage and communication capabilities. In this scenario, Federated Learning (FL) is a rising technology that promise to reduce the amount of data exchanged by robots. Learning is a fundamental step to achieve mobile robots goals and is ubiquitous in problems like Multi Robot Trajectory Prediction (MRTP), Distributed Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (D-SLAM) or Distributed Reinforcement Learning (DRL). In a classic approach a group of mobile robots, acting in the same environment, has to share local data and to append and receive feature from a central unit or to each robot. For example, in D-SLAM a brute-force approach could see every observation vector exchanged between every robot. Each vehicle could then receive any process observation being generated by remote robots, perform a fusing step of this information into a local map of the environment, and update the estimates of its own location and of the other agent location. This approach would surely fall down in huge bandwidth

requirements, as all the observation and control inputs would need to be exchanged. Alternatively, each robot might trivially communicate its control input and observations to a central server or an elected agent that would run a global SLAM filter to estimate the robots and landmark positions. This would put huge computational requirements on the central agent and require that a big covariance matrix be updated with each prediction and observation of each robot.

A FL approach would see, on the contrary, a set of robots that commonly approach a learning problem optimal solution without sharing local observation but only local estimates of the solution. In a Centralized Federated Learning (CFL) network a global average of local estimates is computed by a central agent, while in a Decentralized Federated Learning (DFL) network the optimal solution is reached step by step by local interactions through the network.

In this article, we propose a new framework that integrates a standard modeling for robotic network and a DFL strategy that use the Distributed Stochastic Gradient Descent (DSGD) algorithm, coming to the definition of *Federated Learning Robotic Network* by introducing prior definitions and extensions. We survey existing works on FL and robotics application, and we discuss potential applications in three different robotics fields. By promoting FL in the robotics community, we hope to shift the focus of learning robot's development from a centralized to a distributed methodology.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the details behind the need to get a step further in robotics, integrating the FL strategy. Section III discusses the solutions proposed by the scientific community, in terms of learning and privacy in Multi Robot Systems. Section IV reports the methodology adopted in this paper. Finally, Section V reports the conclusions and presents possible future actions to get steps forward.

II. MOTIVATIONS

Nowadays, we can isolate three determinant contributing factors that have helped in the success of Machine Learning (ML) application for robotics. The first and major one is the large availability on the market of low-cost sensors that can collect a huge amount of data over time. If we think, for example, to LIDAR sensors, we could consider an average production of 10Mb/sec of data used to navigate and localize the robot. The second factor is the large availability of computational power, mainly due to the GPU (Graphic

Processing Unit) technology that can help local devices to train models faster and deploy directly on the robot with less computational costs. Furthermore, we now have on the market AI-ready microcontroller that can train a ML-based model with a percentage of spent power in comparison with a CPU. The third contributing factor is the availability of Deep Learning (DL) Models, which add high-level reasoning capabilities to ML models.

With the rise of the Internet of Robotic Things, security and data privacy are becoming a corner-stone topics of discussion in today's hyperconnected world. Autonomous multi robots applications involves bunches of different machine that collaborate to solve complex tasks in real everyday scenarios. Autonomous vehicles in smart highways are massively increasing the amount of visual and outdoor surveillance. Service robots in industry, hospital and institutions are boosting the amount of personal data and their gathering in indoor environments. Furthermore, Deep Machine Learning techniques makes able the automatic annotations and interpretation of raw data in a practical way. The complex and large nature of this database coming from acting and navigation of autonomous systems in public space, and their sharing on the public internet, are defining critical legal issues. In this context, FL techniques face the problem of giving a privacy-aware framework that does not need to share the training data, enabling each client to voluntarily enter or leave a training process.

The principal drawback of this massive increasing of data from sensors is that the learning phase becomes costly and time-consuming. To face this problem, industry and academia propose to utilize distributed systems to accelerate ML processes. Historically, the first approach was to move computation on the cloud (Cloud Learning) while nowadays the trend is to move the learning on the edge (Edge/Fog Learning). With the advent of commercially available multi robot systems based on Drone or Ground Vehicles, an efficient approach is distributing the learning over a network, with each device communicating only with neighbors. Google introduced FL [1] in a centralized and decentralized version, but Gossip Learning has also been proposed to address the same problem. This approach is fully decentralized, there is no need for parameter server, nodes communicates weight and aggregate models without any intermediation. The advantages of gossip learning are obvious: since no infrastructure is required, and there is no single point of failure, gossip learning enjoys a significantly intrinsic scalability and robustness.

III. RELATED WORK

There is a large literature about distributed optimization algorithm. The seminal work of Nedic et al. [2] focuses on distributed control of networked agents that has to cooperatively minimize a cost function over a decision global vector Θ and prove, under weak assumptions, that the algorithm, approximating and communicating locally, reaches consensus with time varying connectivity. The authors here provide rate of convergence analysis and shows the tradeoff between quality of approximation and computation load. In the paper

of Koloskova et al. [3] a variety of decentralized stochastic optimization methods is studied, and a unified convergence analysis is presented, and convergence rates are provided and compared for convex and strongly-convex case and best known rates for non-convex rates are recovered. The paper of Sun et al. [4] propose the DFedAvgM Decentralized Averaging with momentum, extending the well-known FedAvg approach which is locally implemented on devices connected by an undirected graph and prove the convergence under trivial assumptions. The authors also perform various numerical experiments on IID and Non-IID dataset. Distributed Stochastic Gradient Descent (DSGD) is a common technique to distribute learning over a set of communicating devices. The paper [5] propose a wireless protocol that integrates DSGD in a real scenario by accounting the presence of path loss, fading, blockages and mutual interference.

Bayesian learning is a possible approach treated in a few works by Lalitha et al. In [6] the authors pose the problem of federated distributed machine learning as a special case of the problem of social learning on a graph and, borrowing from Nedic, propose a peer-to-peer social learning scheme where the nodes take a Bayesian-like approach via the introduction of a belief over a parameter space characterizing the unknown global underlying model. Furthermore, in [7] the authors propose a distributed learning algorithm in which users update their belief by aggregate information from their one-hop neighbors to learn a model that best fits the observations over the entire network. The paper [8] propose a FL framework built over a general peer-to-peer network of agents that acts in a variational Bayesian fashion. Local agents keep a local "posterior probability distribution" over the parameter of a global model. The framework allows the training data to remain distributed on mobile devices while utilizing a peer-to-peer model of aggregation in a social network.

FL is introduced in [9] where the authors present a survey of Decentralized Federated Learning (DFL) and its fundamentals in terms of federation architectures, topologies, communication mechanism, security approaches and key performance indicators. Main open source frameworks that support the development of the DFL approach are then introduced and compared. This survey [10] span over the applications of FL for various types of autonomous systems, from industrial robots, through mobile robots, to self-driving car and introduce background concept and terminology used in the ongoing research. In [11] the authors presents three different algorithms for DFL in presence of noise. The authors show theoretical and experimental results studying the impact of noisy communication channels on the convergence of the proposed algorithms. In this paper [12] authors have been compared gossip and CFL. They compare the two approaches in terms of convergence time and model quality, assuming that both approaches utilize the same amount of communication resources and concluding that gossip learning is competitive with federated.

Trajectory generation in Multi Robot Systems is introduced in the seminal paper [13] that shows two different approach for trajectory prediction in a FL framework, a centralized

and a decentralized one. In the first approach a server has the role to aggregate the local estimates, in the second the aggregation is serverless, thanks to a gossip-based share data structure. In both, the learning phase is synchronized by a data-driven mechanism. In [14] a spatial-temporal LSTM encoder-decoder architecture is proposed to solve the vehicle trajectory prediction problem. A spatial attention mechanism is used to obtain inter-vehicle spatial relationship, while a temporal attention mechanism is used to capture the impacts of historical time steps on future trajectory prediction.

Gossip Learning [15] is proposed as a framework for collaborative learning over graph, implementing a virtual weighted voting mechanism over an exponential number of models without any extra cost. The authors also present theoretical proof of convergence and extensive experiments on benchmark datasets. Lossy compressed communication [16] of local parameters between nodes under gossip averaging is also considered. The authors observe that it is beneficial to have multiple gossip steps between subsequent gradient iterations, and claims this as their first work that derives convergence results for non-convex and convex optimization under arbitrary communication compression.

Regarding security of public data, there exist different methods in literature that don't imply data federation. Video Face Anonymization [17] is a method to overcome privacy issues on large picture dataset. The paper propose a similarity-based method that meets two requirements: deanonymization secureness and trade-off control between security and usability in terms of similarity to the original face. Video Surveillance Systems [18] could be affected by severe privacy concerns. Many solutions were proposed for the protection of temporally related objects in consecutive video frames. As a consequence, usability of such systems is severely reduced. This paper proposes a novel VSS which achieves the forementioned tradeoff. Some authors [19] proposed also a new evaluation to analyze the tradeoff between the preservation of privacy offered by filters and the intelligibility of activities that are the subject of the video. As an example, the proposed method issued to compare several commonly employed privacy protection techniques, such as blurring, pixelization, and masking applied to indoor surveillance video. K-anonimization [20] is a common technology for privacy filtering of personal information. The paper shows the applicability of a fuzzy-based clustering technique to a crowd movement analysis problem, in which each personal movement is tracked by face recognition in successive video frames. The authors study the advantage of fuzzy partitions with classic techniques.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In the following, we will introduce a conceptual framework able to model a learning multi-robot systems as a whole and the interactions between the participating robots in terms of federation of learning machine. The framework can be used to model multi-robot learning problem as specified in section III, with a focus on trajectory prediction, distributed mapping and reinforcement learning.

A. Preliminaries: Robotic Network

Here we give a concise summary of the proposed methodology, starting from prior definitions and extending them step by step. We introduce the concept of single mobile robot that include physical state X as the location of the robot and W as the internal processor state. In this section the following definitions from [21] apply:

A *mobile robot* (or interchangeably an *agent*) is defined as a tuple $R = (X, U, X_0, f)$ where

- X is the state space;
- U is the input space;
- X_0 is the set of allowable initial states;
- $f : X \times U \rightarrow R^d$ is a continuously differentiable control vector field that determines the robot motion evolution via the differential equation:

$$\dot{x} = f(x(t), u(t)) \quad (1)$$

We mean that $x \in X$ and $u \in U$ are respectively the *physical state* and the *input space* (position and/or velocity) of the robot.

The whole multi-robot system and the network realized between each robot is modeled as a graph of device, each of them uniquely identified, with edges representing communication between them.

A *robotic network* \mathcal{S} is defined as a tuple $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E})$ where

- $\mathcal{I} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the set of robot's unique identifiers (UIDs)
- $\mathcal{R} = \{R_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}} = \{X_i, U_i, X_i^0, f_i\}$ is the set of mobile robots
- \mathcal{E} is called the *communication edge map*

The interaction between robots is realized through the control and communication law that defines the communication strategy, the alphabet of messages and the state transition for every message received. If the function *msg*, *stf* and *ctl* are identical for every robots the law is *uniform*.

A *uniform control and communication law* \mathcal{CC} for a robotic network \mathcal{S} is a tuple $\mathcal{CC} = (\mathbb{A}, W_i, \{W_i^0\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}, \text{msg}, \text{stf}, \text{ctl})$ where

- \mathbb{A} is the alphabet of messages, exchanged by robots
- W_i is the set of processor states
- W_i^0 is the set of allowable initial processor states
- $\text{msg} : X \times W_i \times \mathcal{I} \rightarrow \mathbb{A}$ is the message-generation function
- $\text{stf} : X \times W_i \times \mathbb{A}^n \rightarrow W$ is the processor-state-transition function
- $\text{ctl} : X \times X \times W_i \times \mathbb{A}^n \rightarrow U$ is the motion-control function

We assume that the whole set of robots are *localized*, so they can sense their own physical position x_i and we also assume that time goes on in a discrete manner as $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ for each robot. Starting from an initial physical-processor state value $(x_0, w_0) \in X_0 \times W_0$, at each time instant k , a robot

i exchange a message (eventually the null message) with each neighbours j computed using the message-generation function msg , then update the value of its processor state using the processor-state-transition function stf . Between computing/communication instants k the robot physical state evolves applying the motion-control function ctl that compute an input for equation (1).

Fig. 1. In [21] the msg , stf and ctl functions are computed subsequently but at the same discrete time instant k . After computing the ctl the physical robot dynamic evolves in time t .

TABLE I
TIME VARIABLES SYMBOL TABLE

Symbol	Value set	Meaning
t	\mathbb{R}	physical time
k	\mathbb{Z}	processor time
τ	\mathbb{N}	learning period

We extend now the framework adding a decentralized federated learning step thus reaching the definition of *federated learning robotic network*. Therefore we suppose that each of N robots has a *local* training dataset and that common goal is to optimize (or train) a *global* model in a collaborative way, without directly sharing any local data.

B. Preliminaries: Federated optimization

A SDOP (Standard Decentralized Optimization Problem) can be written as

$$\min_{\Theta} C(\Theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} c_i(\Theta) \quad (2)$$

where n agents, each having a local objective function aim to reach consensus on $\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$, finding a global optimizer $\Theta = \Theta^*$. The stochastic formulation of the local function c_i is

$$c_i(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\xi_i \sim \mathcal{D}_i} [l(\theta_i, \xi_i)] \quad (3)$$

where ξ_i is the data sampled from the dataset \mathcal{D}_i for the i robots and $l(\theta_i, \xi_i)$ is the local loss function evaluated for each client and each data sample ξ_i . At any iteration of the distributed optimization algorithm each device holds a local numerical approximator $\Theta_i[k]$ for the global closed solution Θ .

The Decentralized Stochastic Gradient Descent (DSGD) algorithm is here used to solve the problem. At each iteration k that is not multiple of τ a local SGD step is computed on local data following

$$\Theta_i[k] = \Theta_i[k-1] - \eta[k] \hat{\nabla} c_i(\Theta_i[k-1]) \quad (4)$$

where η is the learning rate, and $\hat{\nabla} c_i(\Theta_i[k-1])$ is the estimates of gradient computed on a minibatch of \mathcal{D}_i . Otherwise, where the system is in a time instant that is multiple of τ a global optimization step is performed linearly combining the neighbors estimates as in the following equation

$$\Theta_i[k] = \epsilon_{ii} \Theta_i[k-1] + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \epsilon_{ij} \Theta_j[k-1] - \eta[k] \hat{\nabla} c_i(\Theta_i[k-1]) \quad (5)$$

The communication edge map $E = [\epsilon_{ij}]$ establish the connectivity graph for the network, so it can be defined as a stochastic matrix $E \in [0, 1]^{n \times n}$ such that clients i communicates with client j if and only if $\epsilon_{ij} > 0$.

C. Proposed Approach: Federated Learning Robotic Network

In this section we introduce our contribution in terms of state machine extension. We add to the previous state machine two states, respectively `lopt` that triggers the local optimization function (4) and `gopt` that triggers the global optimization function (5). When the robotic network is running in a time instant k that is not multiple of τ then a local gradient descent step is performed on a minibatch of data staying in the `lopt` state, otherwise when the robotic network is in a time instant that is a multiple of the learning period the `gopt` state is reached, the local estimates of θ are exchanged between neighbors robot and a global learning phase start. The entire proposed state machine is showed in fig. 2. The `stf` and `ctl` state behaviors are the same as in the original one, respectively computing the next processor state and the control input for the underlying dynamic differential model.

Established this a *federated learning robotic network* (FLRN) can be defined as a tuple $\mathcal{S} = (\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{E}, \Theta)$ where

- $\mathcal{I} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the set of robot's unique identifiers (UIDs)
- $\mathcal{R} = \{R_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}} = \{X_i, U_i, X_i^0, f_i, \Theta_i, \mathcal{D}_i\}$ is the set of mobile robots
- \mathcal{E} is the *communication edge map*
- $\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the vector of parameter that we want to optimize

Subsequently, the extended *uniform control and communication law* \mathcal{CC} for a federated learning robotic network \mathcal{S} is a tuple $\mathcal{CC} = (\mathbb{A}, W_i, \{W_i^0\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}, msg, stf, ctl)$ where

- \mathbb{A} is the alphabet of messages, exchanged by robots
- W_i is the set of processor states
- W_i^0 is the set of allowable initial processor states
- $msg : X \times W_i \times \mathcal{I} \rightarrow \mathbb{A}$ is the message-generation function
- $stf : X \times W_i \times \mathbb{A}^n \rightarrow W$ is the processor-state-transition function
- $ctl : X \times X \times W_i \times \mathbb{A}^n \rightarrow U$ is the motion-control function
- $lopt : \mathcal{D}_i \times \Theta_i \rightarrow \Theta_i$ is the local optimization function from eqn (4)
- $gopt : \mathcal{D}_i \times \prod_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \Theta_j \rightarrow \Theta_i$ is the global optimization function that implement the global learning equation (5)

Fig. 2. The extended state machine adds the state *gopt/msg* for global learning at time instants that are multiple of τ and *lopt* at time instants that are not multiple of τ .

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we introduced a novel framework that mathematically models a robotic network with distributed federated learning capabilities. The approach is based on the application of the Distributed Stochastic Gradient Descent algorithm to a synchronous network of robots. A new state machine with global and local learning states is presented and explained. We strongly believe that the framework is promising for the modeling of learning-based multi-robot robotic tasks like Trajectory Prediction, Distributed Simultaneous Localization and Mapping and Multi-Robot reinforcement Learning. Future works will implement the methodology using the ROSv2 (Robot Operating System) middleware and will present experiments on simulated and real Multi-Robot Systems.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper is supported both by the Horizon Europe "Trusted Extremely Precise Mapping and Prediction for Emergency Management" project (Grant Agreement, project 101093003 - TEMA).

REFERENCES

- [1] H. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. y Arcas, "Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data," 2023.
- [2] A. Nedic, A. Olshevsky, and C. A. Uribe, "Nonasymptotic convergence rates for cooperative learning over time-varying directed graphs," *IEEE*, 7 2015, pp. 5884–5889. [Online]. Available: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7172262/>
- [3] A. Koloskova, N. Loizou, S. Boreiri, M. Jaggi, and S. U. Stich, "A unified theory of decentralized sgd with changing topology and local updates," 3 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.10422>
- [4] T. Sun, D. Li, and B. Wang, "Decentralized federated averaging," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 4 2022.
- [5] H. Xing, O. Simeone, and S. Bi, "Decentralized federated learning via sgd over wireless d2d networks," *IEEE Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications, SPAWC*, vol. 2020-May, 5 2020.
- [6] A. Lalitha, O. C. Kilinc, T. Javidi, and F. Koushanfar, "Peer-to-peer federated learning on graph," 1 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1901.11173>
- [7] A. Lalitha, S. Shekhar, T. Javidi, and F. Koushanfar, "Fully decentralized federated learning," 2018.
- [8] X. Wang, A. Lalitha, T. Javidi, and F. Koushanfar, "Peer-to-peer variational federated learning over arbitrary graphs," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Information Theory*, vol. 3, pp. 172–182, 7 2022.
- [9] E. T. M. Beltrán, M. Q. Pérez, P. M. S. Sánchez, S. L. Bernal, G. Bovet, M. G. Pérez, G. M. Pérez, and A. H. Celdrán, "Decentralized federated learning: Fundamentals, state-of-the-art, frameworks, trends, and challenges," 11 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2211.08413>
- [10] Y. Xianjia, J. P. Queralta, J. Heikkonen, and T. Westerlund, "Federated learning in robotic and autonomous systems," vol. 191. Elsevier B.V., 2021, pp. 135–142.
- [11] V. P. Chellapandi, A. Upadhyay, A. Hashemi, and S. H. . Zak, "On the convergence of decentralized federated learning under imperfect information sharing," 3 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2303.10695>
- [12] I. Hegedüs, G. Danner, and M. Jelasity, "Decentralized learning works: An empirical comparison of gossip learning and federated learning," *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, vol. 148, pp. 109–124, 2 2021.
- [13] N. Majcherczyk, N. Srishankar, and C. Pinciroli, "Flow-flt: Data-driven federated learning for spatio-temporal predictions in multi-robot systems," *Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 2021-May, pp. 8836–8842, 2021.
- [14] R. Jiang, H. Xu, G. Gong, Y. Kuang, and Z. Liu, "Spatial-temporal attentive lstm for vehicle-trajectory prediction," *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, vol. 11, 7 2022.
- [15] R. Ormándi, I. Hegedüs, and M. Jelasity, "Gossip learning with linear models on fully distributed data," 9 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1109.1396> <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cpe.2858>
- [16] A. Hashemi, A. Acharya, R. Das, H. Vikalo, S. Sanghavi, and I. Dhillon, "On the benefits of multiple gossip steps in communication-constrained decentralized optimization," 11 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2011.10643>
- [17] T. Muraki, S. Oishi, M. Ichino, I. Echizen, and H. Yoshiura, "Anonymizing face images by using similarity-based metric," *Proceedings - 2013 International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security, ARES 2013*, pp. 517–524, 2013.
- [18] H. Du, T. Jung, X. Jian, Y. Hu, J. Hou, and X. Y. Li, "User-demand-oriented privacy-preservation in video delivering," *Proceedings - 12th International Conference on Mobile Ad-Hoc and Sensor Networks, MSN 2016*, pp. 145–151, 6 2017.
- [19] P. Korshunov, C. Araimo, F. D. Simone, C. Velardo, J. L. Dugelay, and T. Ebrahimi, "Subjective study of privacy filters in video surveillance," *2012 IEEE 14th International Workshop on Multimedia Signal Processing, MMSP 2012 - Proceedings*, pp. 378–382, 2012.
- [20] K. Honda, M. Omori, S. Ubukata, and A. Notsu, "A study on fuzzy clustering-based k-anonymization for privacy preserving crowd movement analysis with face recognition," *Proceedings of the 2015 7th International Conference of Soft Computing and Pattern Recognition, SoCPaR 2015*, pp. 37–41, 6 2016.
- [21] F. Bullo, J. Cortés, and S. Martínez, *Distributed Control of Robotic Networks*, ser. Applied Mathematics Series. Princeton University Press, 2009, electronically available at <http://coordinationbook.info>.
- [22] S. Lu, Y. Zhang, and Y. Wang, "Decentralized federated learning for electronic health records," *2020 54th Annual Conference on Information Sciences and Systems, CISS 2020*, 3 2020.
- [23] P. Kairouz, H. B. McMahan, B. Avent, A. Bellet, M. Bennis, A. N. Bhagoji, K. Bonawitz, Z. Charles, G. Cormode, R. Cummings, R. G. D'Oliveira, H. Eichner, S. E. Rouayheb, D. Evans, J. Gardner, Z. Garrett, A. Gascón, B. Ghazi, P. B. Gibbons, M. Gruteser, Z. Harchaoui, C. He, L. He, Z. Huo, B. Hutchinson, J. Hsu, M. Jaggi, T. Javidi, G. Joshi, M. Khodak, J. Konecni, A. Korolova, F. Koushanfar, S. Koyejo, T. Lepoint, Y. Liu, P. Mittal, M. Mohri, R. Nock, A. Özgür, R. Pagh, H. Qi, D. Ramage, R. Raskar, M. Raykova, D. Song, W. Song, S. U. Stich, Z. Sun, A. T. Suresh, F. Tramèr, P. Vepakomma, J. Wang, L. Xiong, Z. Xu, Q. Yang, F. X. Yu, H. Yu, and S. Zhao, "Advances and open problems in federated learning," *Foundations and Trends in Machine Learning*, vol. 14, pp. 1–210, 6 2021.
- [24] A. Nedić and A. Ozdaglar, "Distributed subgradient methods for multi-agent optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 54, pp. 48–61, 2009.

- [25] I. Hegedus, Árpád Berta, L. Kocsis, A. A. Benczúr, and M. Jelasity, "Robust decentralized low-rank matrix decomposition," *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology*, vol. 7, 5 2016.
- [26] D. Shah, "Gossip algorithms," *Foundations and Trends in Networking*, vol. 3, pp. 1–125, 2008.
- [27] M. Jelasity, "Gossip," *Natural Computing Series*, vol. 37, pp. 139–162, 2011.
- [28] V. Mothukuri, R. M. Parizi, S. Pouriyeh, Y. Huang, A. Dehghantanha, and G. Srivastava, "A survey on security and privacy of federated learning," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 115, pp. 619–640, 2 2021.
- [29] J. Zhang, M. Li, S. Zeng, B. Xie, and D. Zhao, "A survey on security and privacy threats to federated learning," *Proceedings - 2021 International Conference on Networking and Network Applications, NaNA 2021*, pp. 319–326, 2021.
- [30] Z. Li, L. Wang, L. Jiang, and C. Z. Xu, "Fc-slam: Federated learning enhanced distributed visual-lidar slam in cloud robotic system," *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics, ROBIO 2019*, pp. 1995–2000, 12 2019.
- [31] X. Zhong, X. Yuan, H. Yang, and C. Zhong, "Uav-assisted hierarchical aggregation for over-the-air federated learning," *2022 IEEE Global Communications Conference, GLOBECOM 2022 - Proceedings*, pp. 807–812, 2022.